

Licensing Best Practices for Sharing Scientific Data

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Please note that this work is a second-edition adaptation of '[Recommended Best Practices for Better Sharing of Climate Data](#),' also licensed [CC BY 4.0](#).

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About Creative Commons

[Creative Commons](#) (CC) is an international nonprofit organization that empowers people to grow and sustain the thriving commons of shared knowledge and culture we need to address the world's most pressing challenges and create a brighter future for all.

Our Vision: A world where education, culture, and science are equitably shared as a means to benefit humanity.

Our Mission: CC empowers individuals and communities around the world through technical, legal, and policy solutions that enable the sharing of education, culture, and science in the public interest.

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Introduction

Open data is central to accelerating scientific progress. One example is how open data was used to bring rapid research and medical clarity during the early phases of the COVID-19 pandemic.¹

In 2023, Creative Commons published [Recommended Best Practices for Better Sharing of Climate Data](#), to contribute to addressing climate change as one of the world's most pressing challenges. The recommendations were created to support the opening of data among the world's large governmental and intergovernmental organizations that produce, collect, publish/host, and/or share public observational data about the earth and the atmosphere. This data is used in climate research and solutions.

CC's initial recommendations were developed in consultation and collaboration with key members of government agencies and intergovernmental organizations² that had taken a strong interest in open practices to produce and publish climate datasets (including observation records), data catalogs, and/or data products (including interpretations and analyses), including:

- European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)
- U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)
- U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)
- UN World Meteorological Organization (WMO)
- Group of Earth Observation (GEO)
- International Organization for Standardization (ISO)
- World Resources Institute (WRI)

As word spread and implementation of the recommendations increased through 2025, CC's climate data work revealed the applicability of the best practices to data producers and publishers/hosts in fields beyond climate data/research. This report is an adaptation of the original, with the goal of applying recommendations to more

¹ Xiaowei Ma, Hong Jiao, Yang Zhao, Shan Huang, Bo Yang, "Does open data have the potential to improve the response of science to public health emergencies?" *Journal of Informetrics*, Volume 18, Issue 2, 2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.joi.2024.101505

² With special thanks to those that consulted with us and contributed to our knowledge for these recommendations, we assert that their participation, while generously helpful, does not inherently represent a commitment to organizational endorsement.

types of scientific observational and experimental data that are publicly shared for inquiry.

This re-release of data sharing recommendations aims to ensure that open data is simple to access and use, and provides guidance that maximizes access, sharing, and reuse of open data, with practical steps that can be implemented today.

Open data is generally defined as openly accessible, editable, and shareable by anyone for any purpose, and generally licensed under an open license.³ Creative Commons open licenses are copyright agreements that grant permission to access, reuse, and redistribute the creator's work with few restrictions. This report concerns scientific data and may not be applicable to other disciplines. For data pertaining to cultural, social, humanities, or other disciplines, we encourage engagement with stakeholder communities for their expertise in an adaptation of these recommendations that is appropriate for their unique copyright considerations and cultural sensitivities.

The recommendations in this report apply to data that was meant to be shared as open data, without additional restrictions. Data with more specific restrictions might fall outside the scope of our recommendations.

³ Adapted from <https://devdocs.webizen.org/PermissiveCommons/PermissiveCommonsTech/WhatIsOpenData/>.

Background

In early 2023, Creative Commons conducted a comprehensive [landscape analysis](#) of major global public climate data sources such as governments, global NGOs, and intergovernmental alliances, assessing their current status and examining their diverse range of data-sharing approaches. The goal was to understand and facilitate more effective sharing of data with open licensing. We reviewed how climate data organizations aligned with the [FAIR Principles](#): findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (see Table 1 below). We also identified and assessed for additional open licensing and open sharing practices.

Table 1. FAIR Principles⁴: Guidelines for making research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (adapted to include open licensing assessments).

<u>F</u> indability	F1. (Meta)data is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier, like DOIs or a standard PID
	F2. Data is described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
	F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data they describe
	F4. (Meta)data is registered or indexed in a searchable resource (e.g., federated searches)
	(Also assessed by CC) Database and/or infrastructure has its own search function
<u>A</u> ccessibility	A1. (Meta)data is retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
	A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
	A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and

⁴ Adapted from <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

	<p>authorisation procedure, where necessary</p> <p>A2. Metadata is accessible, even when the data is no longer available</p> <p>(Also assessed by CC) Data is available to users free of charge</p> <p>(Also assessed by CC) No registration is required in order to access the data</p>
<u>Interoperability</u>	<p>I1. (Meta)data uses a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, in the form of machine-readable file types</p> <p>I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles</p> <p>I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data</p> <p>(Also assessed by CC) Data is downloadable wherever possible</p> <p>(Also assessed by CC) No special software is required to access the data</p> <p>(Also assessed by CC) All data is hosted locally and does not require access to a separate/third party host with less access</p>
<u>Reusability</u>	<p>R1. (Meta)data is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</p> <p>R1.1. (Meta)data is released with a specific, clear, and accessible data usage license</p> <p>R1.2. (Meta)data is associated with detailed provenance</p>

	R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
	<p>(Also assessed by CC)</p> <p>Base data is either dedicated to the public domain using CCO with Attribution Request or is openly licensed with CC BY 4.0 (see Part 1 below)</p>

The recommendations in this report complement the FAIR principles and other existing guidance including the [GEO Data Sharing Principles](#),⁵ the [UN WMO Unified Data Policy](#),⁶ and [CARE principles](#). The recommendations specifically address the gap of ensuring data is openly licensed and shared with open license information via metadata practices that support reuse, attribution, and sharing.

These recommendations are by nature respective of and only applicable to data that may be shared openly and without restrictions, per the allowances of any superseding national laws, security measures, and/or policies. For example, for National Meteorological and Hydrological Services who work with warnings, prohibit derivatives, etc., these recommendations may not be appropriate to apply. Additionally, there are limits to the protection afforded to data and databases under copyright law, which varies by jurisdiction (see [Appendix: Copyright Terms](#)).

⁵ *GEO Data-Sharing Principles state that data, metadata, and products will be shared as Open Data by default, as part of the GEOSS Data Collection of Open Resources for Everyone (Data-CORE) without charge or restrictions on reuse, subject to the conditions of registration and attribution when the data is reused.*

⁶ *WMO Unified Data Policy states that members shall provide on a free and unrestricted basis the core data that are necessary for the provision of services in support of the protection of life and property and for the well-being of all nations, which are required to monitor and predict seamlessly and accurately weather, climate, water and related environmental conditions.*

Part 1: Legal and Licensing Terms

As publicly-shared data is made available for easy access and reuse, it is important to consider the users' legal rights to access and use it. This is often dictated by copyright and licensing (see definitions in Appendix). Legal considerations should not be omitted from conversations about data sharing and legal interoperability. While some existing policies and principles do discuss open sharing of data, or mention the use of data licenses, our recommendations suggest the use of one of two specific legal tools, to be considered and used based on the data producers' needs and context.

Option A

**Creative Commons CC0 Public
Domain Dedication with
Attribution Request**

or

Option B

**Creative Commons CC BY
Attribution 4.0 International
License**

Option A: Creative Commons Global Public Domain Dedication (CC0/"CC Zero") with Attribution Request

Example attribution statement: *"This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CC0 1.0. Attribution is requested. To view a copy of this dedication, visit <http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0>."*

What it is: CC0⁷ is not a license; it is a dedication of the data to the worldwide public domain. Public domain dedication waives copyright and database rights in most jurisdictions around the world. When CC0 is applied to a work, copyright no longer applies to the work in most jurisdictions around the world. In jurisdictions where a public domain dedication is not possible, CC0 provides a maximally permissive fallback option (see Appendix for specifics by jurisdiction). Our recommendation for CC0 with Attribution Request signals the importance of giving

⁷ CC0: <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/>

credit through attribution when using data, even though attribution is not legally required for works in the public domain.⁸

Who it's recommended for: Data organizations developing data policies for the first time; data producers and publishers who are willing to share their data freely in order to maximally reduce the friction in use and achieve the greatest legal interoperability. For data hosts in countries that allow data and database rights, we still recommend Option A (CCO with Attribution Request) in order to dedicate the data and databases to the worldwide public domain. If unable to, we recommend Option B (CC BY).

What it allows users to do: CCO with Attribution Request allows users worldwide to distribute, combine, reanalyze, and build upon the data in any medium or format, with no legal conditions on reuse. Because users always need to review the legal and licensing terms of their data sources and determine what's allowed, data already in the public domain will always be the easiest to use, redistribute, combine, reanalyze, and build upon. Alongside the use of CCO, attribution is requested in a standard format to allow reusers to easily provide credit to the data producer or publisher.

Getting credit through attribution as a professional norm: When using or referencing someone else's work, attribution is widely viewed as an expected and standard professional practice and driver of research and progress, rather than an action arising from legal enforcement and the fear of legal consequences. CCO with Attribution Request requests that data users follow these professional norms and provide attribution. Data providers can ensure they get credit and make it easy for users to provide attribution by providing sample attribution statements adjacent to the work, on their website, and/or as part of their community norms for using their data (for more on attribution, see the section on [Formal Attribution Statements](#)).

Sample text used by UCLA Dataverse: "Our Community Norms, as well as good scientific practices, expect that proper credit is given via citation. Please use the data citation shown on the dataset page."

⁸ Attribution to the original work is a legal requirement of CC licenses. It needs to include, at a minimum, four key components: the author's name, title of the work, the link to the original work (e.g., DOI, website url), and licensing information.

Pros – Maximized reuse and less legal friction: CCO with Attribution Request enables sharing of data with the least amount of friction by removing legal uncertainty around reuse restrictions, thereby maximizing legal interoperability. Users do not need to concern themselves about the legality of their data reuse, saving time that would otherwise be spent deciphering, negotiating, and following complex legal terms and conditions. This legal tool also explicitly specifies disclaimers of warranty that many data providers need in order to distribute their data and reduces time spent paying lawyers to develop and negotiate custom end-user license agreements (EULAs).⁹

Considerations – Proactively managing for sensitive data and misuse:

Organizations with particularly sensitive data can take steps to address any sensitivities before applying CCO with Attribution Request. Organizations may also consider tracking and regulating the use of their name trademarks.

Option B: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)

Example attribution statement: “This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.”

What it is: In some jurisdictions, copyright holders can or must retain data and database rights through copyright, and grant use of those copyrighted works to others using CC licenses. CC BY 4.0 is the most permissive CC license, allowing for unrestricted reuse as long as the work is appropriately attributed. Attribution is a legal requirement of all CC licenses.

Who we recommend for: Data producers and publishers that want to share their data and retain ownership; producers and publishers of forms of data that are copyrightable in nearly all jurisdictions; organizations that have already shared their data under an open license.

⁹ Many data providers want an explicit disclaimer of liability in order to avoid an implication that giving data away freely comes with any warranties or representations. In fact, one way to monetize freely-provided data can be where a reuser wants warranties and representations—the provider can negotiate for payment for taking on that liability. This would be uneconomical to offer for free, as the provider would be taking a financial risk that the reuser will make a claim about the correctness or utility of the data.

What it allows users to do: The CC BY 4.0 copyright license allows users to distribute, combine, reanalyze, and build upon the data in any medium or format, even commercially, so long as attribution is given to the data producer or publisher.

Getting credit through legal requirements: The difference between CCO with Attribution Request and CC BY 4.0, in terms of receiving credit for the work, is that CCO with Attribution Request encourages attribution through professional norms, whereas CC BY 4.0 legally requires attribution through the terms of the open copyright license. With CC BY 4.0, organizations have legal means to pursue action in court for infringement of the license if attribution is not provided. There are cases under this method where attribution cannot be enforced: for example, where the data was not copyrightable in the first place, or where a reuser is making use of the data under exceptions and limitations to copyright such as fair use.

Pros – Property ownership and license enforcement: Where allowed, CC BY 4.0 permits organizations to retain their data as copyrighted property. CC BY 4.0 also creates a stronger mechanism for enforcing attribution through copyright infringement actions or other means such as website takedown requests. This legal enforcement of attribution may also allow data producers to more accurately track attributions as a way to determine the socio-economic benefits of data provision. Data providers can and should use supporting terms and conditions in order to meet any additional organizational needs.

Considerations – License and attribution stacking: Using CC BY 4.0 instead of CCO with Attribution Request can make sharing and interoperability harder down the line, e.g., when the openly licensed data is used to create a derived product by merging it with other openly licensed data. Attributing each source and tracking of changes to the original work (which must also be listed in attribution statements) can become increasingly difficult to track as works and their sources are used and reused hundreds or thousands of times. CC BY 4.0 is not applicable on data that is uncopyrightable, already licensed in a different way, or being used under exceptions and limitations to copyright.

Formal Attribution for Legal and Licensing Terms

Data producers who want to be attributed or are requiring attribution should provide suggested attribution statements that make it simple for others to copy and paste. Formal attribution is a foundational requirement of Creative Commons licensing and a core practice for ethical and lawful data reuse. Attribution ensures that creators and rightsholders are acknowledged, that reuse conditions are transparent, and that downstream users can reliably trace data back to its source.

For compliance via consistent and legally sound attribution, Creative Commons recommends the use of the TASL framework.

Attribution Across CCO and CC BY

Both recommended legal options for data sharing, CCO with Attribution Request and CC BY 4.0, reference attribution, but they do so in different legal ways.

- Under **CCO with Attribution Request**, data is dedicated to the public domain. Copyright and related rights are waived to the fullest extent allowed by law, enabling unrestricted reuse. Attribution is requested as a matter of community norm and scholarly integrity, but it is not legally enforceable.
- Under **CC BY 4.0**, attribution is a legal requirement. It is the sole condition placed on reuse, but failure to attribute constitutes a violation of the license. More generally, all Creative Commons licenses require attribution, and, depending on the specific license, additional conditions may apply that affect redistribution, modification, combination, or derivative use of the data.

In academic, research, and policy contexts, attribution operates alongside established practices such as citation, acknowledgments, and references. While these practices may overlap, license-based attribution remains a distinct legal requirement.

TASL: The Minimum Standard for License Compliance

To meet attribution requirements, a complete and formal attribution must include four elements, commonly referred to as TASL:

- Title (T): The title of the dataset or tool should be included unless no title exists. Where appropriate, it should be accompanied by the copyright symbol

and year of creation, for example ©2026. The title should be hyperlinked to the original source.

- Author (A): The author refers legally to the licensor, copyright holder, or rightsholder. The name should appear exactly as specified by the licensor, including cases where anonymity is requested. The author name may link to a personal, institutional, or catalog page.
- Source Link (S): A URL, DOI, or other persistent identifier indicating where the data can be obtained must be included. This link may be embedded in the title or listed separately. If no link is available, this should be noted along with clear instructions for locating the source.
- License Link (L): A hyperlink to the relevant Creative Commons license deed or public domain dedication page on CreativeCommons.org must be provided.

An example complete and formal attribution is: "[Attributions: Use TASL ©2024](#) is created by Creative Commons and licensed [CC BY 4.0](#)." These elements should be presented clearly and, wherever possible, with hyperlinks that allow users to identify the work, locate its original source, and understand the applicable reuse terms. A printable and downloadable guide explaining TASL for formal attributions is available through the Creative Commons Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/records/14400256>.

License Stacking: Minimizing Friction

Many data projects require gathering data from multiple sources in order to combine them into a resulting derivative data product. While our guidance recommends the use of CCO with Attribution Request or CC BY 4.0 as legal tools, we acknowledge that the current data ecosystem includes many datasets governed by different and sometimes incompatible legal and licensing terms. As a result, data integration frequently introduces legal complexities, with the potential to lead to more restrictive licensing or a situation that requires a lawyer.

These complexities, commonly referred to as "license stacking", can be addressed intentionally, rather than retroactively or not at all. It is important that users feel confident about picking a license for combined or reused data, and confident about navigating what can become complicated stacking scenarios.

In cases where combining or analyzing data involves adding new creative elements, such as prediction modeling from observational data, the original creative elements can be eligible for copyright protection. Even in such cases, best practice is to reduce friction for the field of data users rather than introducing additional restrictions. We recommend data producers and hosts seek to maximize the impact and reach of the work, and choose to license the data using the least restrictive legal terms as possible, with “CC0 with Attribution Request” as default preference if applicable,¹⁰ and CC BY 4.0 as second preference if applicable.

In all, ensure data sources have sufficient rights to release and share work under legal and licensing terms that are as open as possible. In general, data providers are required to maintain compliance with any legal restrictions included with source data, and resulting combined data or products must be licensed accordingly.

To maximize open sharing of data products that have been created from sources with restrictive legal terms, begin by trying to work with those sources to open their data using permissive legal tools. If the source data providers are unable or unwilling to dedicate their data and database rights to the public domain using CC0, the next best option is to work with the source data providers to openly license their data using the most current version of CC BY 4.0. Another option is to try to contractually procure the rights to use and redistribute it using either CC0 with Attribution Request or CC BY 4.0, covering the use of the source data, redistribution of the source data, and distribution of the derived product.¹¹ Although these steps will take more work, they raise the rates of legal compliance and ensure future users can use and freely share the data.

Data Privacy Considerations

Not all data can or should be shared openly. The central problem this guidance addresses is the risk of harm that can occur when data containing sensitive, personal, or protected information is released without appropriate safeguards.

¹⁰ Unless all data sources have been committed to the public domain, CC0 with Attribution Request will not be allowed on a dataset that combines multiple sources with more restrictive licenses, as that would be violating and attempting to override the terms of the sources. If the existing terms and conditions or licenses prevent reuse and/or combining the source data, work with the source data providers to adjust or consider procuring the rights to do so.

¹¹ Here is an example from NOAA: <https://nauticalcharts.noaa.gov/data/data-licensing.html>

Privacy risks, ethical responsibilities, legal obligations, and broader public interests may all require limits on access, reuse, or redistribution. Understanding these risks is essential before determining appropriate licensing or access conditions. These risks can arise in the following contexts:

- Datasets that contain personally identifiable information (PII)
- Datasets that contain information of relevance to national security or public safety
- Review articles and other works of synthesis or opinion/analysis where grantees of a funding organization are invited to contribute on a specific topic

There are valid reasons to restrict data access, including: data that is not to be trained on by AI models without consent, data that is not to be used as public information, data that contains personal information, cases where consent has not been given for release, confidential commercial information, situations where there are sound public reasons for restricting data (e.g. protection of endangered species or archaeological sites), etc. Anonymization techniques, data sharing agreements, and safe havens where data can be accessed in controlled and secure circumstances (e.g., data trusts) can be useful in such cases. When specific legal or ethical restrictions prohibit public sharing of data, private data sharing agreements can be established with those who may obtain access to the data.

If your organization could benefit from support from CC in leveraging these recommendations to design open data sharing policies, craft grant requirements, and/or provide staff training, please let us know by emailing learning@creativecommons.org.

Hosting Other Producers' Data

Many data producers also host their own data in a public platform. However, in some cases a platform might publish data from a different producer(s). If a repository platform has directly published someone else's data for the purpose of hosting (without any alteration), they have not made any copyrightable changes and therefore cannot claim any additional copyright. In this case, the host always inherits and applies the legal and licensing terms used by the source. If publishing

multiple external datasets to a catalog, hosts should aim to apply a universal set of legal terms to the full set of external data when possible. While this may not be possible to do if source data exists under incompatible licenses, it can be desirable to work with the source data provider and ensure the legal right to distribute all data under a standard set of terms. Additionally, publishers/hosts may request acknowledgement, but not as a matter of copyright.

Part 2: Metadata Values for Data Licensing and Attribution

Comprehensive, plain language, and machine-readable metadata maximizes the reusability of data by enabling replication and integration across different contexts. It makes data findable and improves discoverability. It boosts interoperability by providing qualified references to other (meta)data.

There are existing model metadata schemas and standards,^{12,13} including those that address legal license and attribution information. These recommendations address a gap and recommend the persistent use of metadata values that specifically standardize the inclusion of upfront, clear information about attribution, legal and licensing terms, and provenance.¹⁴ Metadata is the best place to be proactive about these critical aspects of interoperability.

Metadata That Supports Formal Attribution

While formal attribution appears in publications, interfaces, and reuse contexts, metadata plays a critical role in ensuring that attribution is accurate, persistent, and reusable across systems. Well-structured metadata allows attribution to travel with data as it is indexed, shared, combined, and reused by both humans and machines.

To support formal attribution at the metadata level, data organizations and repository platforms should ensure that the following values are included in metadata records, expanding TASL (Title, Author, Source link, and License link) to TASLAR (see Figure 1 and Table 2 below), which includes additional elements that strengthen attribution and reduce ambiguity for reusers:

- **Attribution statement (A):** A complete, copy-and-paste-ready attribution or bibliographic citation that includes the TASL of the data and of its sources.

¹² See the W3C DCAT specification: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>, ODI Open Data Rights Statement Vocabulary: <https://schema.theodi.org/odrs/>, and ISO complete list of projects: <https://committee.iso.org/sites/tc211/home/projects/projects---complete-list.html>

¹³ GEO DMP-3: Data should be structured using encodings that are widely accepted in the target user community and aligned with organizational needs and observing methods, with preference given to non-proprietary international standards.

¹⁴ We also recommend organizations reference ISO and DCAT metadata standards for additional guidance for provenance.

These are human- and machine-readable and can be reused without interpretation or guesswork.

- **Rights description (R):** A concise, plain-language summary of how the data may be used, shared, or adapted, based on the full license text.

Figure 1. TASL for Attributions and TASLAR for Metadata

Table 2. Recommended TASLAR Metadata Values for Data Licensing and Attribution, with Examples

Metadata Value Label	Example Value
Title <i>The title of this work is _____.</i>	Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
Author <i>Please list us as the author.</i>	Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA)
Source link <i>The source for this data is (URL or</i>	doi:XXXXXXX/kma.domain

Metadata Value Label	Example Value
<i>doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXXXXXXXXXX¹⁵).</i>	
License link <i>The license link for this data is (URL).</i>	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
Attribution statement <i>Here is a full, copy-pasteable value that includes Title, Author, Source link, and License link that can be used to cite us and our sources:</i>	Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA), doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
Rights statement <i>Here is a statement that provides a summary of the licensing rights and legal terms for this data.</i>	CCO with Attribution Request. This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CCO 1.0, which allows users worldwide to distribute, combine, reanalyze, and build upon the material in any medium or format, with no legal conditions on reuse. Attribution is requested in a standard format to allow reusers to include this information easily.

This expanded structure ensures that attribution is not only complete, but also readily reproducible in downstream uses. The TASLAR fields establish the core information required for legal attribution and may be implemented alongside existing metadata elements within established schemas, rather than replacing them. When embedded in metadata, TASLAR functions as shared infrastructure for attribution, enabling repositories and data stewards to support license compliance, scholarly norms, and technical interoperability simultaneously. This structured approach reduces attribution errors, lowers barriers to lawful and ethical reuse, and helps ensure that credit, provenance, and permissions remain clear as data move across platforms, systems, and contexts.

¹⁵ While metadata standards are flexible with the type of value used for Identifier, we strongly recommend a default use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) wherever possible. These should be used as standard machine-readable components of attribution statements in order to track provenance and understand where data is being used. The host of a data catalog that has published a copy of external data would use a new DOI that links to the catalog. However, links to external data may use their original DOIs.

Because these values are interoperable, they also strengthen data sharing by clearly acknowledging sources and anticipated future uses of data, catalogs, and derived products. They promote user-facing transparency, reduce ambiguity and guesswork, simplify data discovery and comprehension, and support broader accessibility for both human and machine users. Where metadata elements are missing or unavailable, placeholders such as "N/A" should be used to reinforce consistency and standard practice. Doing so supports machine-readable compliance with attribution guidelines, improves interoperability, and enables greater automation in the use, sharing, and integration of data.

Details and definitions of each recommended value are provided in the Appendix, for an example of data published by the Korea Meteorological Administration that is being shared and combined in different ways.

Part 3: General Management and Governance Actions

This section outlines core management and governance actions that support data sharing and ensure that data is not only accessible, but well governed, trustworthy, and positioned for meaningful reuse over time.

Assign a Technical Managing Steward: Designate a responsible party for managing datasets, sourcing, attributions, Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), and their other associated metadata. This responsibility goes beyond ensuring a user-friendly interface; it entails the maintenance of accurate and aligned metadata with the data itself. The accuracy of metadata is essential for maintaining reliability.

Assign a Legal and/or Policy Steward: Designate a responsible party for ensuring governing policy guidelines are adopted and implemented. This includes the recommendations offered herein, alongside any other governance policies that apply. This work is often done in alignment with management, legal, and governing committees and boards, in ways that support the work of the technical managing stewards mentioned above.

Share in Partnership: Intend large datasets for public sharing and reanalysis, in partnership with related organizations/entities. Proactively identify which organizations/entities are users of the shared data and reach out to collaborate in partnership. This is recommended so there is an intentional dialogue that exists between sharing partners, so each may understand their partner's goals, processes, and barriers, and so they may be mindful about co-creating new sharing incentives that meet their needs.

Revisit and Update Regularly: Revisit and update data sharing policies frequently to coincide with evolving practices, technology, and needs. Regularly consult these recommendations to assess and align internal data as it's added.

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We also acknowledge and honor the broader community of practitioners who engage daily in the work of making scientific data more accessible and usable. Their ongoing efforts to improve data practices in service of global knowledge and societal benefit inform the spirit of these recommendations. All contributions were advisory in nature. Participation by any individual or organization does not constitute endorsement of the final recommendations or conclusions presented in this report.

Appendix

Definitions

Copyright Terms

Copyright: Copyright grants to creators a bundle of exclusive rights over their creative works, which generally include, at a minimum, the right to reproduce, distribute, publicly communicate, and make adaptations.

Note that copyright protects original expression and not the particular facts and ideas within a work. This principle limits the copyright protection of some datasets or other material such as mathematical equations, though the selection and arrangement of that material may itself qualify as an original work of authorship. Data producers and publishers must be sure to confirm their data and/or database is legally copyrightable. The exact boundaries of copyright vary country by country, but international treaties provide significant global harmonization. Even where data may not be copyrightable, a data license (or “terms and conditions” or “end user license agreement”) may create contractual limitations that govern the use of data.

Licensing: Licensing gives copyright holders the option to specify the terms for permitted use of their copyrighted material. Licenses are operative only when applied to material in which a copyright exists, and even then only when a particular use would otherwise not be permitted by copyright.

Attribution (vs. Citation): Attribution to the original work is a legal requirement of CC licenses. It needs to include, at a minimum, four key components with their respective links: Title (of the work, followed by the copyright symbol and year, e.g. ©2025), Author (name of author, which could be the publisher of the data), Source Link (link to the original work, e.g., DOI or direct URL), and License Link. These attributions can be and are often provided via citations, which typically already include the former two components: the title of the work and the author’s name. Adding source links and license information to citations ensures well-written citations which also meet the legal requirements of attribution. For more on these four components of an attribution statement, please consult our [“Attributions: Use TASL” resource on Zenodo](#).

Role Types

Data Producer/Supplier: The data producer or supplier creates original data to be shared. They generate data, conduct research to collect and compile data, and are the originators of the information. Data producers, like [Sensor.Community](#), have direct influence on how the data they compile is made available to the public.

Data Host/Publisher: The data host or publisher holds the data for others and is responsible for making the data available to the public. They are commonly staffed with a Data Manager. The data host/publisher may or may not be the creators of the data, but they play a crucial role in facilitating data accessibility. Publishers, such as the Global Earth Observation GEO Knowledge Hub, have taken on the responsibility of making data available to the public by publishing it online, not necessarily exclusive of data sourced by other organizations or initiatives. Publishers have direct influence on how the data they publish is made available to the public.

Sponsors: Sponsors are organizations or entities that invest funds and resources in research for the collection and publication of data. They may have a direct influence on the accessibility of data resulting from sponsored research, even if the data is sourced by another organization.

It is possible for an organization to play more than one of these three roles. For example, NOAA is a U.S. Federal Government agency that works as a sponsor, publisher, and producer of climate data, within its own agency and externally (e.g. the University of Michigan's Great Lakes Environmental Research Laboratory).

Source: The data source is where the data is most directly obtained and serves as a reference for metadata purposes. It indicates one step upstream in the data lineage history, which may or may not be the data producer. The data producer, on the other hand, refers to the origin or provenance of the data lineage history.

Copyright and Database Rights by Jurisdiction

In the U.S., many types of scientific data are considered discoverable "facts," and are thus [not copyrightable](#). Other types of data, such as satellite imagery, may qualify for copyright protection in the U.S. Regardless, data or other works produced by the

U.S. Government are generally not subject to copyright protection in the United States by law (17 USC 105(a)).

In the U.S. and Canada, databases are [only copyrightable under certain conditions](#), specifically when the arrangement and selection of data are sufficiently creative and/or original. However, in Canada the standard for copyrightability of databases can differ and may grant copyright to some database works that the U.S. would not see as copyrightable.

In the [E.U., databases](#) are similarly copyrightable if they are original intellectual creations. In addition, databases subject to copyright protection may also have their content protected by [sui generis database rights](#). Sui generis database rights are distinct from database copyrights, and are applicable under certain conditions if the maker is an EU resident and has made a substantial investment in obtaining, verifying, or presenting the data contained in a database.

Acknowledging the ways in which these rights can vary by jurisdiction, our recommendation is to use the CC BY license in any case of uncertainty or ambiguity. This is because it aligns with best practices and signals the need for attribution.

Sample Metadata Scenarios

In each of the example metadata schemas provided below, we recommend the use of both of two distinct groups of attribution values: the first group provides guidance on how to attribute resulting data, while the second group offers information needed to attribute the sources of that data. The second group can be repeated as needed for additional sources of data used, as demonstrated in our example schema below, where we used “Source 1” to indicate metadata pertaining to the first data source in the series. This is especially useful for users to track the lineage or provenance of the data and understand if and how data has been combined from multiple sources.

Sample Scenario A Metadata for Producing and Sharing Data

Group	Metadata Value Label	Example Value
ABOUT MY DATA/DATABASE/PRODUCT <i>My organization has published something and made it available to share with you, and we want to make sure you attribute it to us and our sources.</i>	Title <i>The title of this work is ____.</i>	Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
	Author <i>Please list us as the author.</i>	Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA)
	Source link <i>The source for this data is (URL or doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXXXXXXXXX).</i>	doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain
	License link <i>The license link¹⁶ for this data is __(URL)__. </i>	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
	Attribution statement	Korean Land and Water Levels

¹⁶ The label “license” can be used to also capture CC0 with Attribution Request as a URL linking to CC0 (<http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0>), which is not technically a license but still sets legal terms.

Group	Metadata Value Label	Example Value
	<p>Here is how to cite us and our sources¹⁷:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● [Our Citation: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link] ● [Our Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link] ● [Our Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link] ● ... etc. 	<p>2003, Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA), doi:XXXXXXX/kma.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0</p>
	<p>Rights Statement</p> <p>Context: Here is a statement that summarizes the licensing rights and legal terms¹⁸ for this data.</p>	<p>CC0 with Attribution Request. This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CC0 1.0, which allows users worldwide to distribute, merge, reanalyze, adapt, and build upon the data in any medium or format, with no legal conditions on reuse.</p> <p>Attribution is requested in a standard format to allow reusers to include this information easily.</p>
<p>ABOUT MY SOURCE(S)</p>	<p>Source 1 Title</p> <p>Context: The title of our first</p>	<p>N/A</p>

¹⁷ This metadata value provides the user a complete and copy-paste-ready attribution statement combined from the previous values provided.

¹⁸ For CC0 with Attribution Request: "This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CC0, which allows users worldwide to distribute, merge, reanalyze, adapt, and build upon the data in any medium or format, with no legal conditions on reuse. Attribution is requested in a standard format to allow reusers to include this information easily." For CC BY 4.0: "This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. The CC BY license allows users to distribute, merge, reanalyze, adapt, and build upon the data, even commercially, in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the data producer or publisher."

Group	Metadata Value Label	Example Value
<p>My organization got data from other sources, and <u>we want to make sure we attribute our sources.</u></p>	<p>source¹⁹ is ____.</p>	
	<p>Source 1 Author</p> <p>Context: our first source came from __(author)__.</p>	N/A
	<p>Source 1 Source link / Identifier</p> <p>Context: The source link / identifier for our first source is __(doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXXXXXXX)__.</p>	N/A
	<p>Source 1 License link</p> <p>Context: The license link for our first source is __(URL)__.</p>	N/A
	<p>Source 1 Attribution statement</p> <p>Context: Here is the citation of our Source 1 and their sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [Our Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link] • [Source 1's Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link] 	N/A

¹⁹ Showing the name (or other identifying text) improves the user experience by allowing users, producers, and suppliers to visually confirm the data source they are linking to is correctly associated with the source data/catalog/product.

Group	Metadata Value Label	Example Value
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="435 283 836 409">• <i>[Source 1's Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i><li data-bbox="435 430 609 451">• ... etc.	

Sample Scenario B

Metadata for Hosting Others' Data

Group	Metadata Value Label	Example Value
<p>ABOUT MY DATA/DATABASE/PRODUCT</p> <p><i>My organization has published something and made it available to share with you, and <u>we want to make sure you attribute it to us and our sources.</u></i></p>	<p>Title</p> <p><i>The title of this work is _____.</i></p>	KMA Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
	<p>Author</p> <p><i>Please list us as the author.</i></p>	Climate Data Store (CDS)
	<p>Source link / Identifier</p> <p><i>The identifier for this data is __ (doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXXXXX XXXX) __.</i></p>	doi:XXXXXXXX/cds.domain
	<p>License link</p> <p><i>The license link for this data is __ (URL) __.</i></p>	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
	<p>Attribution statement</p> <p><i>Here is how to cite us and our sources:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>[Our Citation: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>[Our Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>[Our Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>... etc.</i> 	KMA Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, Climate Data Store, doi:XXXXXXXX/cds.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0 , CCO with Attribution Request; Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, Korea Meteorological Administration, doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0 , CCO with Attribution Request
<p>Rights statement</p>	CCO with Attribution Request.	

	<p><i>Context: Here is a statement that previews the licensing rights and legal terms for this data.</i></p>	<p>This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CCO 1.0, which allows users worldwide to distribute, merge, reanalyze, adapt, and build upon the data in any medium or format, with no legal conditions on reuse.</p> <p>Attribution is requested in a standard format to allow reusers to include this information easily.</p>
<p>ABOUT MY SOURCE(S)</p> <p><i>My organization got data from other sources, and <u>we want to make sure we attribute our sources.</u></i></p>	<p>Source 1 Title</p> <p><i>Context: The title of our first source is ____.</i></p>	Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
	<p>Source 1 Author</p> <p><i>Context: our first source came from __(author)__.</i></p>	Korea Meteorological Administration
	<p>Source 1 Source link / Identifier</p> <p><i>Context: The identifier for our first source is __(doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXXXXXXXXX)__.</i></p>	doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain
	<p>Source 1 License link</p> <p><i>Context: The license link for our first source is __(URL)__.</i></p>	CCO with Attribution Request
	<p>Source 1 Attribution statement</p>	Korea Meteorological Administration, Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, 01/01/2004,

	<p><i>Context: Here is the citation of our Source 1 and their sources:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>[Our Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> ● <i>[Source 1's Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> ● <i>[Source 1's Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> ● <i>... etc.</i> 	<p>doi:XXXXXXX/kma.domain, CCO with Attribution Request</p>
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Sample Scenario C

Metadata for User Combining Two Datasets into a New Product

Group	Metadata Value	Example Value
<p>ABOUT MY DATA/ DATABASE/ PRODUCT</p> <p><i>My organization has something to share with you, and we want to make sure you attribute us and our sources.</i></p>	<p>Title</p> <p><i>The title of this work is _____.</i></p>	<p>User's Org</p>
	<p>Author</p> <p><i>Please list us as the author.</i></p>	<p>Land and Water Levels Across Asia 2003</p>
	<p>Source link / Identifier</p> <p><i>The identifier for this data is __ (doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXX XXXXXXXX) __.</i></p>	<p>doi:XXXXXXXX/user.domain</p>
	<p>License link</p> <p><i>The license link for this data is __ (URL) __.</i></p>	<p>CC BY 4.0</p>
	<p>Attribution statement</p> <p><i>Here is how to cite us and our sources:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>[Our Citation: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> ● <i>[Our Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> ● <i>[Our Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> ● <i>... etc.</i> 	<p>User's Org, Land and Water Levels Across Asia 2003, 31/10/2024, doi:XXXXXXXX/user.domain, CC BY 4.0;</p> <p>Climate Data Store (CDS), KMA Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, 21/05/2004, doi:XXXXXXXX/cds.domain, CCO with Attribution Request; Korea Meteorological Administration, Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, 01/01/2004, doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain, CCO with Attribution Request;</p>

		Japan Meteorological Agency, Japanese Land and Water Levels 2003, 01/01/2004, doi:XXXXXXXX/jma.domain, CC BY 4.0.
	<p>Rights statement</p> <p><i>Context: Here is a statement that previews the licensing rights and legal terms for this data.</i></p>	This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0, which allows users to distribute, merge, reanalyze, adapt, and build upon the data, even commercially, in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the data producer or publisher.
<p>ABOUT MY SOURCE(S)</p> <p><i>My organization got data from other sources, and <u>we want to attribute our sources.</u></i></p>	<p>Source 1 Title</p> <p><i>Context: The title of our first source is ____.</i></p>	KMA Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
	<p>Source 1 Author</p> <p><i>Context: our first source came from __(author)__.</i></p>	Climate Data Store (CDS)
	<p>Source 1 Source Link / Identifier</p> <p><i>Context: The identifier for our first source is __(doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXX XXXXXXXX)__.</i></p>	doi:XXXXXXXX/cds.domain
	<p>Source 1 License link</p> <p><i>Context: The license link for our first source is __(URL)__.</i></p>	CCO with Attribution Request

	<p>Source 1 Attribution statement</p> <p><i>Context: Here is the citation of our Source 1 and their sources:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>[Our Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>[Source 1's Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>[Source 1's Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>... etc.</i> 	<p>Climate Data Store (CDS), "KMA Korean Land and Water Levels 2003", 21/05/2004, doi:XXXXXXX/cds.domain, CCO with Attribution Request; Korea Meteorological Administration, "Korean Land and Water Levels 2003", 01/01/2004, doi:XXXXXXX/kma.domain, CCO with Attribution Request</p>
	<p>Source 2 Title</p> <p><i>Context: The title of our second source is -----.</i></p>	<p>Japanese Land and Water Levels 2003</p>
	<p>Source 2 Author</p> <p><i>Context: our second source came from __(author)__.</i></p>	<p>Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA)</p>
	<p>Source 2 Source link / Identifier</p> <p><i>Context: The identifier for our second source is</i></p>	<p>doi:XXXXXXX/jma.domain</p>

	<p>__(doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXX XXXXXXXX)__.</p>	
	<p>Source 2 License link</p> <p><i>Context: The license link for our second source is __(URL)__.</i></p>	<p>CC BY 4.0</p>
	<p>Source 2 Attribution statement</p> <p><i>Context: Here is the citation of our Source 2 and their sources:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>[Our Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>[Source 2's Source 1: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>[Source 2's Source 2: Title, Author, Source link / Identifier, License link]</i> • <i>... etc.</i> 	<p>Japan Meteorological Agency, Japanese Land and Water Levels 2003, 01/01/2004, doi:XXXXXXXX/jma.domain, CC BY 4.0</p>